

How can we identify endogenous quality criteria?

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The empirical study of the quality criteria researchers apply when they assess each other's work is currently lacking a methodological discussion about the suitability of the available methods for this purpose. This is partly due to the missing theoretical foundations including the reluctance by scholars to define the concept of research quality itself. Starting from a concept of research quality as a collective frame of a scientific community, I discuss the conditions under which five approaches to the empirical study of field-specific quality criteria are applicable and the informational yield of these approaches.

1. Introduction

For a long time, science studies scholars have been interested in the criteria which researchers apply when they assess the work of their colleagues, for example in the peer review of journal articles or the peer review of grant proposals. These assessment situations are endogenous in the sense that the context and purpose of the assessment is the collective production of knowledge by a scientific community, in which the utility of knowledge claims for others' research is scrutinized (Gläser, 2024).¹

Methods that have been used to reconstruct quality criteria held by researchers include surveys (e.g. Langfeldt, Reymert & Aksnes, 2021; Hug & Ochsner, 2022), interviews (Guetzkow, Lamont & Mallard, 2004; Lamont, 2009) or combinations of it (Hug, Ochsner & Daniel, 2013; Lewandowska et al., 2023), the content analysis of grant proposals and reviews of them (e.g. Hartmann & Neidhardt, 1990; Reinhardt, 2010; Barlösius, 2019) as well as review reports of journal manuscripts (Horbach, 2021).

Surprisingly, the application of these methods is not informed by a methodological discussion about their validity, i.e. about the extent to which their application does indeed reconstruct endogenous quality criteria. Are there methods which are more suitable than others to identify endogenous quality criteria? Which methods are applicable to specific assessment practices? How are methods rooted in a theoretical concept of research quality, and what are the methodological implications of that concept?

The aim of this paper is to provide first answers to these questions for some of the methods that can be used to reconstruct quality criteria. Starting from a theoretical concept of research quality, I discuss the potential of several empirical methods I used for reconstructing endogenous quality criteria in specific assessment situations.

The methods were used in a project examining how field-specific quality criteria are embedded in a field's research practices (Laudel, 2024). Over the time span of three years I investigated the use of quality criteria in plant biology, experimental ultrafast laser physics, and medieval history.

¹ Assessment situations are hybrid if criteria of actors outside the scientific community are included in the assessment process. For example, funding agencies may include exogenous assessment criteria like the applicant's career stage (Laudel, 2024).

2. The conceptual approach and its methodological consequences

The validity of an approach – the extent to which it measures what it is supposed to measure – can only be assessed if it operationalises a theoretical concept. This is why it is important to start from a definition of research quality. I draw on a definition of research quality as a specific collective frame of a scientific community that “organises the assessment of contributions, research processes and fellow producers to determine their utility for individual and communal knowledge production processes” (Gläser 2024, p.4). Frames can be defined as specific cognitive structures that provide knowledge about situations and proven solutions for typical problems (Schütz, 1967). As collective frames, quality frames are latent phenomena of which researchers are only partially aware. They organise the perception and assessment of situations. Collective frames are constantly reconstructed and changed through interactions in the scientific community. They are enacted by researchers in specific situations, and the ways in which frames are enacted depends on the situations. Situations in which quality frames are enacted include everyday decisions on which papers to read or which epistemic resources to use, discussions at seminars and conferences and the writing of grant proposals or publications (ibid: p.7) as well as formal situations of explicit assessment like peer reviews. In all these situations quality assessments are processes of knowledge construction in which those who assess research quality simultaneously construct objects of assessment, evaluation criteria, and the assessment that follows from the application of the criteria.

This conceptual starting point challenges a common approach that is based on asking researchers what they mean by ‘research quality’. These approaches create situations in which researchers are compelled to explicate their understanding of research quality to investigators they perceive as outsiders rather than members of their scientific community. Not surprisingly, these approaches circle around very general ‘given’ criteria, such as originality, validity, reliability, scientific value and so on and specify what these criteria mean to researchers from different fields (e.g. Lamont, 2009, p.2-4).

However, if quality criteria are part of quality frames of a scientific community which are constructed in specific assessment situations, then

- researchers are only partially aware of such criteria and partially able to explicate them (Hug et al., 2013: 370; Ochsner, Hug & Daniel, 2016, p.50),
- quality criteria must be derived from the analysis of situations in which community members enact quality frames for each other rather than outsiders, and
- assessment situations must be treated as embedded in field-specific research and communication practices.

From the definition of research quality as a collective frame follows that identifying quality criteria requires the analysis of endogenous assessment situations in which quality frames are enacted. I analysed the communication of researchers in such situations by applying several approaches which are discussed in detail in the next section. The assessment situations varied in their degree of formality: from formal assessment (peer review of manuscripts and grant proposals) to more informal research discussions at seminars and conferences.

3. The potential of different methods for identifying endogenous quality criteria

3.1 Content analysis of open peer review documents of journal articles:

Some journals include the comments of the reviewers as well as the responses of the authors alongside the published articles. If one of these journals is a core journal of a scientific

community, i.e. if most of its articles are authored by members of this community, the documents of the open peer review can be used for identifying a community's quality criteria. The review documents published in the journals *Nature Communication* and *The Plant Cell* were analysed to study quality criteria in ultrafast laser physics and plant biology. The documents included extensive communications between reviewers, editors, and authors. The original manuscript to which the reviewers' comments referred was not available.

Reviewer comments were carefully read and searched for indicators of quality assessments (Figure 1). Indicators for negative assessments included reviewers complaining about missing information in the text, wrong statements, things that should have been done differently, or statements that could not be understood or believed. Indicators for positive assessments included statements about the utility of the presented research or parts of it for the community the ingenuity of the experimental approach, or the quality of the writing.

Figure 1: Example of an argument made by a reviewer of a manuscript of the journal "The Plant Cell" and of the authors' response.

Major Criticisms:

1. One of the major ideas that this paper forwards is the repression and deacetylation of histone H3 at the G1 promoter. However, in figure 3D, the authors do not control for endogenous H3 levels in the ChIP, and the amount H3 total at the promoters should be measured in the different mutant backgrounds. Otherwise, the authors cannot distinguish between changes in nucleosome density and an actual change in post-translational modifications.

Response: Thank you for your critical advice. We checked endogenous H3 levels on the G1 promoter using ChIP and the result is described in our answer to Specific issues, point #4, above. The revised manuscript includes this control (Supplemental Figure 5).

Analysing the arguments requires gaining basic knowledge about research processes in the field and to comprehend the technical language. Some technical terms (such as "ChIP") might require background reading. Interpreting a reviewer's argument can be facilitated by reading the responses of the authors and by using the published version of the article as an additional context. The quality criterion (here: completeness of the approach²) could be identified, using an inductive approach of open coding and subsequent comparing codes for consistency.

3.2 Content analysis of book reviews

Book reviews are publications in which researchers provide summaries and assessments of the content of books published by their colleagues. Book reviews can be understood as *ex-post* open peer reviews where the identities of the author and the reviewer are known. They are particularly useful sources in fields such as history where monographs and edited books are important publication genres. While the reviews of monographs in medieval history I analysed contained both summaries of the arguments and quality judgments (for an example see figure 2), reviews of edited books predominantly contained summaries of their content and very few quality judgments, which made them less suitable for the identification of quality criteria.

The analysed book reviews were much shorter than the peer review documents discussed in the previous section. The very condensed arguments and the low degree of standardisation of the historians' language made it sometimes difficult to derive at quality criteria. However,

² "Completeness" means here the inclusion of all experiments and procedural steps that are necessary to produce valid results. For example, missing control experiments were frequently criticized in reviews (Laudel, 2024).

identifying quality criteria was possible. Indicators of negative assessments included, among others, statements about the wrong or superficial interpretation of sources or about presentism (the application of contemporary concepts to the reconstruction of the past). Indicators of positive assessments included for example statements about the utility of the book or the sources used by the author for the community or praise of the quality of the analysis.

In a first step, I read the whole review and marked the parts which contained assessments (Figure 2). The parts which summarised the content of the book I used as context for analysing the assessment. Although the material that is assessed (the book) could be in principle drawn at as an additional context, this is - given the length of books - rather impractical. I then interpreted each assessment and identified the quality criteria applied by the author of the review. In the text presented in Figure 2 the plausibility of the interpretation, the comprehensiveness of sources and the analytical depth could be identified as quality criteria³.

The assessments in book reviews are very likely to be influenced by the openness of the review process. Indeed, German historians on non-tenured positions tended to voice much less criticisms in their book reviews than their professorial colleagues. Nevertheless, I found many cases where historians openly expressed their criticism when they believed that the work fell short of their quality standards. Due to their explicit language such book reviews were particularly suitable for identifying quality criteria.

Figure 2: Excerpt of a book review of a monograph in medieval history

³ The plausibility of an interpretation is the extent to which it is logically and empirically possible in the absence of definitive evidence; the comprehensiveness of sources is the extent to which a set of sources is sufficient to answer a research question; the analytical depth of the research process describes the extent to which the presented analytical tools are actually applied to the empirical evidence (Laudel, 2024).

3.3 Observations of internal research seminars

A third method to investigate communications in the field were research seminars. These seminars had a rather informal character. They were organised by one or few professors working in the same field. In seminars in all three fields, group members gave talks about their work in progress, and invited guest speakers to present their work in progress or completed work. Presenters gave a talk of half an hour to one hour, which was followed by a discussion lasting 15 minutes in the two sciences fields or up to 45 minutes in history seminars. The incompleteness of most of the presented research enabled the observation of assessments of phases of the research process which would receive less attention on other occasions, such as the formation of research problems. Another advantage was that presentations of research in progress were met with more critical judgments because discussants wanted to help shaping the research.

The discussions of the audience comprised of three types of questions and comments: questions that sought more empirical information (e.g. “What is the reason for choosing this TMDC [material]?”), questions focused on a quality assessment (e.g. “What you have presented to us seems to be very speculative”), and requests for information whose inclusion could improve the research but which did not include explicit assessments (e.g. “Which purpose had the text at the time it was produced?”, which alludes to the criterion “contextualisation of sources”). Only the second and third type of questions were included in the analysis. One of the main challenges is to distinguish between the first and third type of questions. To facilitate the interpretation of questions and comments, the presentations could be utilized as context. In seminar discussions, questions and answers were formulated less precisely than in written reviews, which made their analysis more demanding. However, the informal character of the evaluation situation meant that the discussants often expressed their arguments and concerns more explicitly than in the more public communication situations. In the excerpt of field notes in Figure 3, the correctness of an interpretation of an empirical result is contested.

Figure 3: Fieldnotes of a discussion at an internal seminar in plant biology

Discussant: Slide 12, weighted gene co-expression network. When we look at the quantum yield and the light intensity it is completely reciprocal. And this is actually wrong, the light intensity increases, the quantum yield decreases. Plants react to this high light stress also with this photochemical quenching. [explains mechanism] ... This is actually a systemic process, in this process there is no gene expression involved.

Presenter: True, we cannot measure reactions that are regulated by genes directly. But if these reactions are affected by stimuli like light intensity or temperature, they affect other genes. I expect that we can see that effect indirectly through ROS reactions and homeostasis reactions that are catalyzed. Indirectly we can see some links to ROS mechanism and also ROS stress damage that happens in the cell.

Discussant: The only thing in my opinion you can really measure is the damage they do, not the concentration.

3.4 Observations of conferences

Quality assessments were also observed in more formal scientific meetings, namely at scientific conferences. Particularly in the two sciences fields, presentation and question times were usually much shorter than in informal seminars, and longer exchanges between a presenter and a discussant were very rare. Instead, presenter and discussant continued their discussion as one-on-one conversations during the break following the session. These exchanges could not be observed. Poster sessions provided better opportunities for observations because authors of

posters presented their work - usually intermediate results – to anyone who was interested, which made being part of the audience easy.

There was a large variation in discussions with regard to questions being asked at all and with regard to questions containing assessment criteria. Quality assessments were less likely to occur at large and thematically broad conferences. If such questions were raised in interactions at a poster, I could participate as an observer or by asking questions myself to understand the observed interaction (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Fieldnotes of a discussion at a poster session at a physics conference

Experimentalist:	We've got some really good [specific experimental] data .
Theorist:	Oh yes, they're really good .
Observer:	Why are they really good data ?
Theorist:	Because they provide a lot of information about the [material]. You always need information about these three things: spin, lattice, electrons. But often, you don't have all of them, and you fit the ones that are missing.

3.5 Semi-structured interviews

Interviews can be a suitable method for identifying quality criteria if they are focused on assessments experienced by interviewees rather than abstract questions about quality criteria that are important in the interviewee's field. I asked researchers in the three fields to share reviews they received for their manuscripts and grant proposals as well as the reviewed texts. This approach enables the inclusion of a wider range of material like articles in journals without open peer review, rejected journal articles, and reviews of grant proposals (access to which would otherwise depend on negotiations with funding agencies).

Figure 5: Interview excerpt of a discussion about a journal review the interviewee received

<p>Interviewer: Yeah, then there was this aspect with the “overexpression”. [...] And in the response, it was said [...]: "This was shown by different methods and not necessarily relying on overexpression from a strong viral promoter." So there's something wrong with this overexpression. That's what I was trying to understand.</p> <p>Plant biologist: Well, overexpression experiments can indeed be problematic because they may cause the protein being studied to be produced in much larger quantities within the cell than is usually the case. This could, for example, result in the protein being transported to somewhere it doesn't belong and then suddenly performing a different function [...]. That's why these overexpression experiments should always be approached with caution.</p>
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Before the interview, I analysed the material provided by interviewees in a similar way as the open peer review files. I then used the interviews to discuss selected reviewer judgments with the researcher. This enabled a deeper understanding of the arguments that were made and a probing for possible reasons why a certain argument was made (see Figure 5 for an example). Since the arguments and criteria they contained were produced by community members for

community members and not by the interviewee for the interviewer, the interviews did not produce stylized versions of general quality notions but enabled the exploration of endogenous quality criteria. Interviews with historians addressed reviews of books they authored or edited and book reviews they had written themselves. No problems of confidentiality arose because all material was in the public domain.

4. Discussion

In this short paper I could only provide brief descriptions of the five approaches of empirically identifying endogenous quality criteria. Further analytical steps and the results (field-specific quality criteria) are published elsewhere (Laudel 2024).

All five approaches avoided the pitfalls of forcing researchers to enact quality criteria for an outsider. Even the interview approach presented here is deeply rooted in the internal communication of scientific communities. The approaches were adjusted to field-specific practices, e.g. by applying content analysis to open reviews of journal articles in the sciences and to book reviews in the humanities, or by observing poster sessions in the two science fields. Observations of conference talks at large and thematically diverse conferences were less suitable for identifying quality criteria. The potential of specialised conferences or workshops for this purpose needs further exploration.

The main drawback of analysing endogenous assessment situations is the necessity to gain an understanding of a field's research processes and to understand its technical language. This seems to be much harder to achieve in fields like experimental physics, which uses a highly codified language and where experimental work is based on theoretical concepts which are difficult to grasp by social scientists. The difficulties of obtaining this expertise limit the fields a single sociological observer can study comparatively.

5. Conclusions

If 'research quality' is a collectively constructed frame of members of a scientific community rather than a set of properties of research results that just needs to be discovered, then researchers are likely to present research quality differently when they talk to outsiders (sociological observers) compared to interactions with members of their field. It is therefore necessary to identify criteria of research quality in situ. Otherwise, their modification for the use in policy contexts or hybrid assessment situations cannot be understood. The sociology of science provides methods that can obtain this information.

Competing interests

None.

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Open science practices

Some of the empirical data used in this paper are open to the public, namely the open peer review files of journal articles and partially the book reviews. Fieldnotes from conference discussions and interviews are not shared due to confidentiality issues. Particularly in seminar discussions researchers are presenting preliminary results, learn the trade as early career researchers and meet criticism in a protected environment. Sharing observational data about

these events would violate explicit and implicit confidentiality agreements. Seeking an explicit agreement of the observed researchers to data sharing after the observation would jeopardize the future willingness of researchers to be observed in these informal situations.

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